

RESTRUCTURING THE BITLIST 2025

Neil Jefferies

*Open Preservation Foundation &
University of Oxford*

UK

*neil.jefferies@openpreservation.org
0000-0003-3311-3741*

Sarah Middleton

Digital Preservation Coalition

UK

*sarah.middleton@dpconline.org
0000-0002-7671-403X*

Abstract – The BitList of Endangered Digital Species [1] was first published by the Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC) [2] in 2017 as an advocacy tool, highlighting the risks associated with digital materials and consequently the need for Digital Preservation. However, as the size and complexity of the digital world has grown, so has the BitList and its associated maintenance. Towards the end of 2024, the DPC enlisted the help of a diverse group of regular BitList contributors to review the structure and processes associated with the BitList with a view to streamlining the review process while retaining or improving its utility to users. This paper describes a work-in-progress and will be updated with the outcomes of this process.

Submission Type – Short Paper

Keywords – Risk, Review, Monitoring, Advocacy

Conference Topics – Tūhono - Connect.

I. BACKGROUND

The BitList of Endangered Digital Species was first published by the Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC) in 2017 as an advocacy tool, highlighting the risks associated with digital materials and consequently the need for Digital Preservation. It is produced and maintained by a panel of experts and practitioners with widely differing backgrounds, knowledge and expertise drawn from the digital preservation community. It has undergone a comprehensive review every two years with an interim progress report and commentary in alternate years.

However, as the size and complexity of the digital world has grown, so has the BitList and its associated maintenance activities. In 2024, prior to the start of

the BitList review process, the DPC enlisted the help of a group of regular BitList contributors (the BitList TaskForce – see Acknowledgments) to review the structure and processes associated with the BitList with a view to streamlining the review process while retaining or improving its utility to users.

After an initial brainstorming session, the taskforce was split into two subgroups which were tasked with reviewing the structure of the BitList and its review processes, respectively. Mindful of the interdependence of the two aspects, the subgroups met periodically during the subsequent process to ensure joined up thinking.

II. INITIAL BRAINSTORMING - SUCCESS CRITERIA

An initial session of the whole group was convened with a view to identifying the perceived shortcomings of the BitList and its review processes, and to define the desired outcomes of the activity. The following issues were identified:

1. There isn't a clear definition of what constitutes a "digital species" in the context of the BitList. Over time, this has resulted in some species that are quite similar, or that overlap in some respects, which can potentially make navigation and review more complex.
2. While the BitList was designed as an advocacy tool we had little information about how it is actually used in practice, and which aspects work well or otherwise. It is available in both document and online

- versions, with the online edition offering different navigation and discovery routes.
3. The overall categorisation of species has not been reviewed since the inception of the BitList, yet this content structure is used as the basis of the review process - both for dividing up tasks and also allocating tasks to the relevant experts. Many species potentially appear in several categories, yet are only reviewed in the context of one, resulting in a review process that could be somewhat incongruous. Some entries could risk being reviewed by people with mismatched expertise.
 4. The review processes are quite informal, the interaction between the DPC and the reviewers is quite discursive which is becoming less scalable over time. A more formal process, with better defined roles and responsibilities, and an accompanying reviewers guide would improve efficiency and help newcomers. The current two-year cycle of in-depth reviews alternating with updates should also be reviewed.
 5. There is a need to engage more widely, especially with industry domain experts outside the heritage sector, to improve the coverage of the BitList. Outwith this exercise there should be some community outreach plans alongside the next review cycle, aided by improved transparency and documentation around the BitList processes.

The structure and layout of the online and document versions of the BitList should be updated to reflect the outcomes of this exercise. In addition, there are an increasing number of other digital preservation resources available (COPTR, ICRFF), providing more detail on tooling, policies etc. that would be useful to link to the BitList in some way.

III. PROCESS SUBGROUP

Given that the BitList review process is partly dependent on the structure of the BitList, it made sense to defer analysis until a clearer idea of the outcomes of the restructuring process had emerged. In turn, any new structure should take into account

how users approach and use the BitList in practice, and not break existing workflows known to be effective. An initial task for the Process Review subgroup was therefore to develop an understanding of how and why users used the current BitList offerings, making use of two sources of information.

- Use case blog postings by DPC members about the BitList that provided a verbal narrative around usage
- A survey of DPC members [3] about the BitList (including those who had not used it)

A number of key observations about the BitList emerged, which feed into the activities of the Structure Review subgroup.

- Although users did use the BitList primarily for advocacy, a number also used it as an informal preservation monitoring service, making use of the Critically Endangered and Endangered categories to feed into their preservation planning processes. Thus, the risk level classifications have proved useful, and this use-case suggests that linking to related resources would be a useful addition.
- A number of users focused on the technical categories of endangered species (file formats and storage technologies) where obsolescence was a primary risk, with a view to identifying technologies to avoid or migrate away from. Other use cases focused on the type of data under threat (such as personal archives or museum collections) where the threats are more socio-economic. This suggests that a categorisation by risk type might be useful.
- Both the online and document (PDF) version of the BitList were found to be useful to the majority of users, although navigating to a specific species of interest in the online version was a frequent use case.

The next phase will be to examine the current two-year review process in the light of the outcomes of the Structure Review to see if it remains effective and/or efficient, mindful that the process is undertaken by volunteers drawn from the DPC

membership. For example, it may make sense to target higher risk categories for more frequent review unless there are external factors that dramatically affect a particular species. Alternatively, it may make sense to focus on species for which there do not exist good policies or techniques for mitigation. Review of the overall structure and allocation of species within that structure should also happen regularly, though on a longer timescale such as five years.

Restructuring of the BitList might also reveal gaps in coverage by the current review team which would necessitate further outreach and recruitment before the 2025 cycle got underway.

In any case, the 2025 review cycle would be somewhat experimental, testing and, hopefully, validating the work of the subgroups with the wider BitList review community. Once validated, the process can be codified in a review guide for future use.

IV. STRUCTURE SUBGROUP

Before considering the structure of the BitList the subgroup tried to tackle the question of defining what constitutes a “digital species” in the context of the BitList. The original term is borrowed by analogy from the CITES List of Endangered Species [4] where a taxonomic species was originally defined along the lines of “a set of animals or plants in which the members have similar characteristics to each other and can breed with each other” [5]. So, breeding aside, was it possible to identify the common characteristics of the “species” comprising the current BitList to codify an appropriate definition?

Analysing the current list, a number of observations emerged:

- A number of very similar entries appear in several places (e.g. *online games*, *phone games*, *smart-tv games*, *console games*) which end up having very similar descriptions and risk profiles. These suggest that some species might simply be varieties¹ that could be merged for brevity.
- Equally, some of the current categories used to group species are not clearly distinct. Taking the example above, *online games*

could reasonably appear under *Gaming*, *Web*, *Cloud* and/or *Apps*. The *Social Media* category overlaps heavily with *Web* and *Cloud* too. This suggests that these categories might be better implemented as keywords.

- In other cases, such as *Sensitive Data*, the species seems to represent a risk factor linking disparate entries rather than a natural grouping of data types and varieties.
- There was a lot of repetition in species risk profiles. This is not unexpected - however you define a digital species, material has to be stored in some form and there is consequently attendant technical risk due to obsolescence. In terms of highlighting risks peculiar to a particular species it would be less repetitive to cross-reference the relevant technology species. This would also simplify the review process.

Taking these findings into account, the emergent defining characteristic of each species appears to be the nature of the unique risks associated with them. These appear to fall more or less into three clusters, which somewhat align with some of the use-cases identified in the survey:

- Organisational - species where the primary threats are social, political, economic or legal in nature and thus primarily human mediated and mitigated.
- Platform - species where the threats are related to design choices made by the content creators/publishers, often involving multiple parties with differing goals. These include proprietary, networked and cloud-based systems. This is an interesting result because complexity is not really addressed in many threat taxonomies.
- Technical - species characterised by threats related to obsolescence and fragility/failure where traditional mitigations such as replication, migration and emulation apply.

While these clusters could form the basis of a more taxonomic approach to the BitList, this is likely to be limited by the fact the most species are likely to

¹ Continuing the biological analogy

be subject to multiple, albeit related, threats. One of the goals of any new proposed structure was that everything currently on the list should "fit" without requiring mental gymnastics. An initial pass through the BitList was carried out and suggests that this is indeed the case, with a few caveats:

- The risk-oriented classification tends to group similar species together in way that suggests it might be possible to merge/deduplicated a number of species. It also tends to group species in a way that aligns well with the expertise profiles of reviewers.
- It is very evident that cross referencing is essential since risks inherently always cascade down to those resulting from underlying technology choices. This is not only a powerful way of simplifying entries, and the accompanying the review process, but a useful reminder to users of this aspect of the digital preservation challenge.
- The old categories are still useful as keywords, and, in fact, can become more expressive and accurate since several keywords can apply to a species instead of just one.
- Some species, as currently defined, appear to have a potentially hierarchical relationship with others (which breaks the biological analogy somewhat). For example, *Oral Histories* and *First Nations Secret/Sacred Cultural Material* could be seen as specific cases of *Politically Sensitive Data*.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The BitList taskforce brought together a group of people from widely differing background with a shared interest. The analyses carried out by the subgroups appears to suggest adopting a risk-oriented primary structure for the BitList - which makes a lot of sense given its objectives and review processes. It also suggests several ways that the list, and consequently the review process could be simplified and made more efficient. This remains to be proved as the 2025 review begins later in the year.

However, when considering the use-cases of the BitList as a resource, it is also evident that the existing discovery routes – based on somewhat

loosely defined categories (reimagined as keywords), and risk levels – remain valid and useful. In addition, use of the Bitlist beyond advocacy, for policy and planning, suggests that improved links to other DP resources such as the International Comparison of Recommended File Formats (ICRFF) [6].

REFERENCES (HEADING 4)

- [1] The Global 'Bit List' of Endangered Digital Species <https://www.dpconline.org/digipres/champion-digital-preservation/bit-list>
- [2] Digital Preservation Coalition <https://www.dpconline.org/>
- [3] Community feedback sought on the DPC's Global 'Bit List' of Endangered Digital Species <https://www.dpconline.org/news/bit-list-community-feedback-2025>
- [4] Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species <https://checklist.cites.org>
- [5] Cambridge Dictionary definition: species <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/species>
- [6] The International Comparison of Recommended File Formats <https://openpreservation.org/resources/member-groups/international-comparison-of-recommended-file-formats/>

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Neil Jefferies is Innovation Specialist for the Centre for Digital Scholarship at the Bodleian Libraries, University of Oxford. He is also Executive Director of the Open Preservation Foundation, and a Director of Data Futures GmbH. He is co-creator of International Image Interoperability Framework and the Oxford Common File Layout.

Sarah Middleton is Chief Community Officer at Digital Preservation Coalition. She is responsible for promoting and raising awareness of digital preservation through and with international stakeholders, whilst supporting and fostering an active and growing community of members around the world.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS – THE BIT LIST TASKFORCE

DPC: Sarah Middleton, Michael Popham, Amy Currie

Process Subgroup: Sara Thomson (University of Edinburgh), Angeline Takawira (United Nations), Meghan Lyon (Library of Congress)

Structure Subgroup: Neil Jefferies (University of Oxford, Open Preservation Foundation, Data Futures GmbH), Kevin Long (Royal Irish Academy), Sofie Niemi (Swedish Tax Agency)

